

Incremental nonlinear dynamic inversion-based attitude control for a morphing wing UAV

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Abstract. A morphing wing can create an optimal aerodynamic shape for different flight regimes, such as take-off, cruise, and landing, thereby minimizing energy use during flight and improving sustainability of flying. The use of meta-materials in the structure of the wings allows for smooth morphing transition between the wing box, the leading and the trailing edges. The contribution of this article is the design and evaluation of an automatic flight control system that is able to control the airplane under aerodynamic model uncertainties due to changes in the wing shape. The controller uses a cascaded design of non-linear dynamic inversion (NDI) and Incremental non-linear dynamic inversion (INDI) structures. The outer loop NDI controller uses a kinematic transformation to calculate angular rates needed for the inner loop INDI rate controller. The INDI controller uses dynamic inversion of the control effectiveness model to predict the required control surface deflections. The incremental part of the INDI controller reduces the dependency on the full aerodynamic model.

Keywords: Flexible leading edge, flexible trailing edge, variable camber, morphing wing, INDI, NDI

1 Introduction

Aviation is relatively new compared to the animal flight, which has undergone millions of years of evolution. This evolutionary process is reflected in animals' ability to adapt their body shape to different flight regimes. The first fully controlled, powered flight was achieved by the Wright brothers, who used wing-twisting technology to generate roll moments. The lightweight structure of their aircraft enabled such morphing capabilities. As aircraft development progressed and aircraft became larger, morphing wings were replaced by rigid wings with dedicated control surfaces. However, advances in material science and manufacturing technologies have enabled the creation of novel structures that make use of metamaterials. The mechanical properties of metamaterials are determined by the unique geometry of their microstructures or cells, allowing for the design of structural components with tailored mechanical characteristics. By using metamaterials [1–3] it is possible to optimize flexibility and stiffness and achieve desired deformed shapes. This process, known as wing morphing, reduces aerodynamic drag by eliminating gaps and discontinuities commonly found in conventional wing designs [4, 5]. A morphing wing can continuously adapt its shape to optimize performance across various flight regimes, providing the best lift over drag coefficients for take-off, cruise, loitering and landing. However, it brings new challenges in control in contrast to a control of rigid wing aircraft with conventional control surfaces like ailerons and flaps.

Morphing a wing by changing its shape generally affects the aerodynamics in a non-linear way. This means that linear controllers, such as PID controllers, are not the most suitable choice for controlling a morphing wing. In this paper two nonlinear control approaches based on feedback linearization are used: Nonlinear Dynamic Inversion (NDI) and Incremental Nonlinear Dynamic Inversion (INDI). NDI requires an accurate model of the controlled plant, which is then inverted to find the control law. In INDI, a part of the model information is replaced by sensor measurements. This reduces the dependency of the controller on model information, which is especially useful when the controlled plant is hard to model or contains uncertainties. For INDI control, only the part of the model that directly relates to control effectiveness is required. Both NDI and INDI control has been applied to flight control problems in the past, both on simulation models [6], UAV's [7–9] and even flight tested on business jet type aircraft [10]. The control performance of INDI has been demonstrated in aerial docking applications, such as successful docking of a refueling probe under turbulent conditions [11], and in controlling the angular rates of wing-docked multibody UAVs [12].

Incremental control strategies are used for their reduced dependency on a precise model of controlled plant. For example, in [9], INDI is used to control a tail-sitter UAV, for which the transition from vertical to horizontal flight regime is too complex to model precisely. Another example of how INDI can be used is in [10], where an INDI controller is used to suppress unwanted aeroelastic effects, such as flutter, and for wing load alleviation in general. Other recent advances in morphing wing control rely on different control methods. In [11], a data driven extremum seeking method is used to alleviate the hinge moment on a morphing tail.

Since the control of a morphing wing involves additional degrees of freedom, control allocation [13–16] can be applied to introduce a secondary control objective alongside the primary one. Daisy-chaining [17] is a commonly used strategy for distributing control commands among different actuators according to a defined priority.

The contribution of this article is an incremental flight control system design for a UAV with morphing control surfaces. An inner loop rate control system and outer loop attitude control system is designed and a control allocation method is implemented to distribute the requested control moment to the different actuators.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 outlines the methodology of the (I)NDI control law design, its implementation on the morphing-wing UAV, and details of the controller realization in MATLAB/Simulink. Section 3 presents the results of the controller design and performance evaluation and discusses their limitations, and Section 4 provides the conclusions.

2 Methods

The reference UAV, together with the inputs defined by the roll requirements, is presented in the following subsection. Subsequently, the NDI and INDI control laws are introduced, and their application to the morphing wing is analyzed. The section is concluded by daisy-chaining control allocation strategy description.

2.1 Reference UAV Design

Fig. 1. Reference UAV model visualized by AVL software

A reference UAV has been defined to serve as a baseline for the new morphing wing design. The wing shape is adapted from Smart-X project [18] and the tail unit was designed proportionally to the wing to ensure stable configuration in both longitudinal and lateral stability. The reference UAV is intended solely as a model for evaluating

the benefits of the morphing wing and for conducting control analyses. Its geometry, see **Fig. 1**, was analyzed using the Athena Vortex Lattice (AVL) software. The stability and controllability derivatives are presented in **Table 3** in the Appendix. The main design parameters of the reference UAV are listed in **Table 1**.

Fig. 2. Each wing consists of five ribs numbered from root of wing

Table 1. Reference UAV properties

Property	value unit
Mass:	50 kg
Wingspan:	3.8 m
Length:	2 m
Wing planform shape:	Rectangular
Wing chord length:	0.6 m
Control surface area of main wing:	40 %
Maximal allowed aileron deflection:	10 °
Maximal actuator speed:	20 °/s

The maximum trailing-edge deflection of 10° is derived from roll analysis and requirements specified in certification specifications [19] paragraph 157, for take-off and approach flight phases. This requirement demands the ability to reverse a 30-degree banked turn to the opposite direction within 4 seconds. Additionally, recommendations are provided for maximum non-dimensional roll rates, which should not be less than 0.09 for high maneuverability aircraft [20]. These values are used as criteria for control simulations. The relatively low value of the trailing-edge deflection is due to the morphing trailing edge exceeds the typical aileron size in both spanwise and chord-wise directions.

2.2 Control Design

This subsection provides the methodology of the designed control system, starting with a general formulation of NDI and INDI control laws, followed by the specific control

structure (inner/outer loops), tuning of control gains and control allocation described in the following subsection.

NDI Control Design.

A generic control-affine nonlinear system can be written as

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)u \quad (1)$$

$$y = h(x) \quad (2)$$

where x is the state of the system, y is the output of the system, u is the control input of the system and f , g , h , are nonlinear functions describing the relationship between input, state and output. The idea behind NDI control is to take derivatives of the output y , until the input u appears in the expression of the derivative for y . Once that happens, this relationship can be inverted to find the expression for u in terms of some derivative of y . For example, if taking one derivative of y results in an expression that contains u , this means a system of relative degree 1, then we get:

$$\dot{y} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \dot{x} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (f(x) + g(x)u) = F(x) + G(x)u \quad (3)$$

$$u = G(x)^{-1}(v - F(x)) \quad (4)$$

where v is the virtual control that will be controlled in an outer loop. With this choice of u , the nonlinear system has been linearized and decoupled, such that a linear controller can be designed to control v . From the equation above, it can be seen that G must be invertible. This corresponds to the requirement that the control effectiveness of the system does not go to zero, since then an infinite control would be commanded.

INDI Control Design

Incremental NDI also utilizes feedback linearization, but its derivation is different from regular NDI. Consider a general nonlinear system:

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u) \quad (5)$$

Where x is the state, u is the input, and f describes the dynamics of the system. Note that for INDI, there is no requirement for the system to be affine in the input, as was the case for NDI.

The first step is to apply a Taylor series expansion on f , resulting in:

$$\dot{x} = f(x_0, u_0) + \left. \frac{\partial f(x, u)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0, u=u_0} (x - x_0) + \left. \frac{\partial f(x, u)}{\partial u} \right|_{x=x_0, u=u_0} (u - u_0) + \Delta \quad (6)$$

Under the assumption of time scale separation, where the effect of the input on the state derivative is larger than the input of the state on the state derivative, the state related part in the equation above can be neglected, such that we get:

$$\dot{x} = \dot{x}_0 + G(x_0, u_0)(u - u_0) \quad (7)$$

This assumption is known to be reasonable for rate control systems for aircraft when the actuators are fast enough [6]. Besides this assumption, the higher order terms in the Taylor expansion are assumed to be negligible and the value of f at the linearization point is assumed to be measurable, i.e. obtained from a sensor measurement. From here on, a similar approach to NDI is taken. The control law is determined by inverting the equation above and replacing the state derivative with a virtual control v :

$$u - u_0 = G(x_0, u_0)^{-1}(v - \dot{x}_0) \quad (8)$$

An observation in comparing the INDI control law with the NDI one is that INDI no longer depends on the full model since the F part is removed. Another difference is that, due to the linearization step, the control law for INDI is derived in terms of control increments. To get the total control input at any timestep, the control increment of the current timestep is added to the total control from the previous timestep.

2.3 Simulation Implementation

The control loop begins with the NDI outer loop, where Euler angles are prescribed. From these, the angular rates are evaluated and passed to the inner INDI loop, see **Fig. 3**. The INDI controller generates the required roll moment, which is then translated by the control allocation module into deflection commands for each control surface. These commands are processed by the actuator dynamics model, resulting in the actual control surface deflections. Finally, the system model computes the corresponding state-space response.

The controller testing environment was implemented in Simulink, a block-diagram environment within MATLAB. Both the simulation and the controller run at 100 Hz, which is a typical frequency for aircraft of this scale. Each simulation represents a flight with pre-defined Euler angles and/or angular rates at given time steps, which the controller is tasked to follow. Controller performance was evaluated by measuring the difference between the actual flight attitude and the reference, as well as the difference between the actual and the prescribed angular rates.

The maneuverability requirement originates from the specified roll maneuver, defined as a transition from a 30° bank in one direction to a 30° bank in the opposite direction. To test this, a 60-second simulation of repeated flight maneuvers was conducted, consisting of alternating roll angles of $+30^\circ$ and -30° with a switching period of 5 seconds. The tracking error between the UAV's target and actual positions was quantified using the root-mean-square (RMS) method.

Fig. 3. Inner loop block diagram

Daisy-Chaining

The control allocation is applied with using daisy-chaining method. The control allocation goal is to achieve maximum control surface efficiency and minimum consumed power of actuators at the same time. The input variable is desired roll moment and the output are deflections of all control surfaces. The general idea of the control allocation is depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Control allocation block

The daisy-chaining strategy is motivated by the primary goal of achieving the best control efficiency relative to the hinge moment. A secondary objective is to ensure that the deflection difference between two adjacent segments does not exceed 5 degrees. That bound comes from limited flexibility of the trailing edge. The control law is expressed mathematically by **Chyba! Nenašiel sa žiaden zdroj odkazov.** and **Chyba! Nenašiel sa žiaden zdroj odkazov.** where x_i denotes the input roll moment at each stage, g_i represents the control efficiency of each stage, and y_i is the resulting stage deflection.

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 5 & x_i \frac{1}{g_i} > 5 \\ -5 & x_i \frac{1}{g_i} < -5 \\ x_i \frac{1}{g_i} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$x_{(i+1)} = x_i - g_i(y_i) \quad (10)$$

The daisy-chaining sequence (see **Table 2**) is derived from the control effectiveness and hinge moment of each actuator. The corresponding control effectiveness values are provided in **Table 3** in the Appendix. Both hinge moments and control effectiveness were obtained from the AVL model. The wing segments are numbered from root to tip, with each connected to a dedicated actuator. The stages represent the stepwise sequence of segment deflections. Each segment is actuated in two stages: first up to 5 degrees of deflection, and then, in a subsequent step, up to 10 degrees.

Table 2. Binary matrix used for mixing of signals from Daisy-chaining groups to actuators

		Actuator no.				
		1	2	3	4	5
Stage	1	✓				
	2	✓	✓			
	3				✓	
	4			✓	✓	✓
	5					✓
	6			✓		
	7		✓			

3 Results and discussion

The on-board estimate of the control effectiveness was systematically varied to evaluate its influence on trajectory tracking. The controller maintained stable aircraft behavior across a broad range of model mismatches. When the on-board control effectiveness values were lower than the actual values, the system response exhibited oscillatory behavior. In contrast, higher values resulted in reduced responsiveness, with the controller following the reference trajectory more slowly. A total of 30 simulations were conducted, each lasting 60 seconds and consisting of alternating roll maneuvers ranging $\pm 30^\circ$ every 5 seconds, (see **Fig. 5**).

Time to reach desired bank angle when switching from 30° to bank in opposite direction was reached at 1.67 seconds within 3° difference (95% accuracy) and in 2.41 seconds within 0.6° difference (99% accuracy).

Fig. 5. Tracking performance of all axis. Roll is using left Y axis, pitch and yaw are using right Y axis.

Fig. 6. Tracking error in roll axis

During these tests, only the on-board control effectiveness parameter was varied, within the range from $-10,000$ to -0.01 , using different step sizes to capture behavior around the optimal value. The optimal setting the control efficiency parameter was determined as -2.9936 . Higher absolute values correspond to increased controller effectiveness. The negative sign arises from the convention that a negative aileron deflection produces a positive roll about the longitudinal axis. The tracking error in bank angle is shown in **Chyba! Nenašiel sa žiaden zdroj odkazov.**

The control allocation using the daisy-chaining method results in stepwise increases in the deflections of all actuators. The sequence is illustrated in **Fig. 7**, where the deflections correspond to a continuously increasing target roll moment. The diagram also indicates the order in which the actuators are engaged. Actuators 3 and 5 operate simultaneously until reaching a deflection of 5 degrees.

Fig. 7. Dashed line corresponds to right Y-axis. Graph shows effect on actuator deflection to gradual increase of desired roll moment. The order is set in CA block. CA also ensures that maximal deflection between adjacent segments is not larger than threshold of 5° for this test case.

The simulation yields more precise results compared to a simple unsteady roll analysis as defined in [20]. This analytical solution is derived from a single equation of motion with one degree of freedom. Using this method, the time required to achieve a 60° roll with a servo rate of $20^\circ/\text{s}$ was calculated as 1.62 seconds, assuming an asymmetric full trailing-edge deflection of 10° . This value corresponds to time to roll get from simulation of 1.67 seconds with 95% accuracy. These results were obtained for a maneuvering speed of 33.2 m/s. At a landing speed of 17.5 m/s, the time to achieve a 60° roll increases to 2.19 seconds. Therefore, the roll requirement specified in the certification specifications [19] can be considered satisfied across the full flight speed range.

Fig. 8 presents a comparison of cumulative hinge moment estimates with and without the daisy-chaining strategy. The plot also includes the scaled difference between the two results. A hinge moment reduction of 6–8% was observed for roll moments ranging between 1.2 and 2.5 Nm. At low roll moments, a slight increase in cumulative hinge moment can be seen when control allocation is applied. This occurs because the inner actuator provides the best ratio of hinge moment to control efficiency, which results in slightly greater control surface deflection compared to the case where all actuators are used simultaneously.

Fig. 8. Comparison of hinge moments to generated roll moment. No CA uses single aileron, CA works with five independent actuators.

The limitations of this study should be acknowledged. The simulation relies on control surface efficiency data generated by the AVL software, which is subject to significant model simplifications. Consequently, the aerodynamic analysis must be interpreted with caution. However, the control efficiency values are derived from lift distribution analysis at low angles of attack and small control surface deflections, conditions under which vortex lattice methods generally provide reliable results. Comparisons of AVL with other approaches typically show deviations in stability derivatives of up to 20% relative to analytical methods [21], and in some cases more than 100% when compared to wind tunnel measurements [22]. Since this research focuses solely on theoretical reference drone geometry, a highly precise model is not essential. Moreover, the INDI controller is not strongly dependent on the accuracy of the model, allowing the assumption that moderate inaccuracies in the stability and control derivatives do not critically affect the controller design.

The AVL modelling also brings a limitation on the calculation of the control effectiveness terms for the different control surfaces. Each surface has its own control effectiveness, but this is assumed to be constant and independent of the other surfaces. In reality, deflecting one surface will affect the airflow and hence the effectiveness of the neighboring surfaces. More advanced computational fluid dynamic tools could be used to improve the fidelity of the control effectiveness computation. The Simulink model simplifies the system by neglecting the dynamic loading of the actuators. Aerodynamic forces are not considered and are assumed to have no effect on the actuator's speed,

which is kept constant. Additionally, physical imperfections, such as backlash in mechanical joints and material hysteresis, are not included in the analysis.

4 Conclusion

This work presents the design of a cascaded NDI–INDI controller with daisy-chaining control allocation for a morphing wing UAV. Simulation results demonstrate accurate attitude tracking and robustness to model mismatches, with roll requirements from certification standards satisfied across the full flight speed range. The daisy-chaining strategy contributes to a reduction of hinge moments by 6–8% under representative conditions.

While the aerodynamic data is obtained from a simplified vortex-lattice model, the INDI controller’s limited dependence on model precision ensures reliable performance. Future research will extend this work by incorporating more detailed actuator dynamics and validating the approach through experimental testing on physical prototypes.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.J.; methodology, K.J. and Z.P.; software, Z.P., K.J. and P.J.; validation, Z.P.; data curation, P.J.; writing, Z.P., K.J. and P.J.; visualization, P.J.; supervision, K.E. and Z.P.; funding acquisition, K.J. and Z.P.

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Data Availability Statement

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found at:
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Conflicts of Interest.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Table 3. Nondimensional roll moment coefficient derivatives by control surface deflection

Derivative	Value
Cl_d1	-0.000614
Cl_d2	-0.001959
Cl_d3	-0.002782
Cl_d4	-0.003017
Cl_d5	-0.001233

Table 4. Asymmetric stability derivatives of the reference UAV

Cy_beta	-0.213227	1/rad	side force coeff. derivative due to sideslip angle
Cy_p	0.049037	[-]	side force coeff. derivative due to roll rate
Cy_delta_r	-0.002822	1/deg	side force coeff. derivative due to rudder deflection
Cl_beta	-0.023938	1/rad	roll moment coeff. due to sideslip angle
Cl_delta_a	-0.004555	1/deg	roll m. coeff. due to all aileron segments deflection
Cl_delta_r	0.000089	1/deg	roll moment coeff. due to rudder deflection
Cl_p	-0.456237	[-]	roll moment coeff. due to roll rate (roll damping)
Cl_r	0.068653	[-]	roll moment coeff. due to yaw rate
Cn_beta	0.092372	1/rad	yaw moment coeff. due to side slip angle
Cn_delta_a	0.000031	1/deg	yaw m. coeff. due to all aileron segments deflection
Cn_delta_r	-0.001302	1/deg	yaw moment coeff. due to rudder deflection
Cn_p	-0.019136	[-]	yaw moment coeff. due to roll rate
Cn_r	-0.091642	[-]	yaw moment coeff. due to yaw rate (yaw damping)

Table 5. Symmetric stability derivatives of the reference UAV:

Cm_alpha	-0.959453	1/deg	pitch moment coeff. derivative due to angle of attack
Cm_delta_e	-0.022346	1/deg	pitch moment coeff. derivative due to elevator deflection
Cm_u	0.072476	[-]	pitch moment coeff. derivative due to velocity
Cm_q	-9.371126	[-]	pitch moment coeff. derivative due to pitch rate
Cx_alpha	0.122305	1/deg	x-axis force coeff. derivative due to angle of attack
Cx_delta_e	0.000176	1/deg	x-axis force coeff. derivative due to elevator deflection
Cx_u	-0.006646	[-]	x-axis force coeff. derivative due to velocity
Cz_alpha	-4.744823	1/deg	z-axis force coeff. derivative due to angle of attack
Cz_delta_e	-0.009362	1/deg	z-axis force coeff. derivative due to elevator deflection
Cz_u	-0.422947	[-]	z-axis force coeff. derivative due to velocity
Cz_q =	-8.267364	[-]	z-axis force coeff. derivative due to pitch rate